

Data Transfer

First read the text about data transfer using the image above

***Vereist**

1. Which of the following steps does Professor Hutseepluts need to take to secure * the data, some of which are personal? (multiple answers possible)

Vink alle toepasselijke opties aan.

- Contact a data management expert to discuss how to secure the file transfer from the audio device/photo camera to a laptop
- Contact a data management expert to discuss back-up(s)
- Contact a data management expert to help out with the data classification
- Contact a legal expert to discuss the border transfers of personal data and local legislation
- Contact a legal expert to discuss if other legal safeguards or agreements are necessary
- Speak to IT to discuss encryption and secure transportation
- Contact a legal expert to find help with filling out a Data Protection Impact Assessment

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